

1 **PROGLACIAL LAKE EVOLUTION COINCIDENT WITH GLACIER**
2 **DYNAMICS IN THE FRONTAL ZONE OF KVIÁRJÖKULL, SOUTH-EAST**
3 **ICELAND**

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24
25 **Abstract**

26 The termini of Icelandic glaciers are highly dynamic environments.
27 Pronounced changes in frontal ablation in recent years have consequently
28 changed ice dynamics. In this study we reveal the inter-seasonal dynamics
29 of the Kviárjökull ablation zone and proglacial zone using ArcticDEM and
30 Sentinel-2 images acquired between 2011 and 2021, and intra-seasonal
31 dynamics with repeated UAV surveys during summer 2021. Average glacier
32 surface velocity in the ablation zone ranged from 51 m yr⁻¹ in 2015 up to
33 199 m yr⁻¹ in 2018, with maxima within the axial zone of the glacier and
34 minima on the glacier edges. Coincidentally, and in accordance with glacier
35 retreat/advance, the ice-marginal proglacial lake fluctuated in its area and
36 we interpret that it was also a key factor in the development of the glacier
37 terminus morphology. A complex spatial pattern of glacier surface elevation
38 changes, including thickening in the frontal true left margin of the terminus,
39 are interpreted to be due to variable subglacial topography, relatively fast
40 ice flow from the accumulation zone and an insulating effect of glacier
41 surface debris cover. In contrast, the true right (southern) part of the
42 glacier terminus experienced thinning and retreat/disintegration also during
43 the 2021 summer season, which we attribute to enhanced frontal ablation
44 connected to the intrusion of lake water into the crevassed glacier terminus.
45 Overall, this study suggests that where glaciers are developing ice-marginal
46 lakes complex patterns of glacier dynamics and mass loss can be expected,
47 which will confound understanding of the short-term evolution of these
48 environments.

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50 **Keywords:** ablation zone, ice flow velocity, surface elevation changes,
51 glacial lakes

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1. INTRODUCTION

54 Glaciers and ice caps have been losing mass at an enhanced rate during the 21st
55 century across the globe (Hugonnet et al. 2021; Millan et al. 2022) because of
56 atmospheric and oceanic warming. This has profound implications for marine and
57 lacustrine ecosystems (Arrigo et al., 2017; García-Rodríguez et al., 2021), as well
58 as having a multitude of socioeconomic impacts. Additionally, glacier retreat can
59 alter the frequency and severity of natural hazards (Motschmann et al., 2020),
60 particularly with respect to the formation and evolution of glacial lakes (Carrivick
61 and Tweed, 2013) and glacier lake outburst floods (GLOFs) (Carrivick and Tweed,
62 2016). Glacier evolution and lake evolution both affect how water resources are
63 managed (Immerzeel et al., 2020). Glaciers with terminus lakes tend to have
64 faster-flowing ice and higher rates of mass loss (King et al., 2018; Sutherland et
65 al., 2020; Carrivick et al., 2020, 2022).

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67 Icelandic glaciers and ice caps are of particular interest because they contain a
68 disproportionately large amount of Europe's freshwater resources, with some of
69 the thickest glaciers in the world (Immerzeel et al., 2020). This resource is of great
70 importance for the people of Iceland because 73 % of their electricity is sourced
71 from hydropower (Hjaltason et al. 2018). Additionally, the tourism sector in
72 Iceland is beginning to suffer the consequences of retreating glaciers, as
73 accessibility to some sites is becoming more challenging (Welling and Abegg,
74 2021). This access challenge is concerning because tourism contributes to 8 % of
75 Iceland's GDP (Statistics Iceland, 2021). To best manage Iceland's water and
76 energy security, as well as its economic prosperity, research into Icelandic glacier
77 dynamics is essential.

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79 Like glaciers and ice caps worldwide, Iceland's glaciers have been in continual
80 decline since the Little Ice Age (LIA), except for a cool period between 1980 and
81 1993, when a glacier mass gain of $1.5 \pm 1 \text{ Gt year}^{-1}$ was recorded (Björnsson et
82 al. 2013). In recent decades, this rate of decline has increased, with half of the
83 total mass loss since the LIA having occurred since 1994 (Aðalgeirsdóttir et al.
84 2020). Although Iceland is particularly susceptible to ice mass loss, as the effects
85 of climate change are amplified in polar regions (Holland and Bitz, 2003), the rate
86 of deglaciation has been reduced since 2011 as a result of North Atlantic regional
87 cooling (Noël et al. 2022). Iceland's volcanic activity also plays an important role
88 in controlling glacier retreat, with volcanic dust and tephra affecting the albedo of
89 ice caps and geothermal activity contributing to subglacial melt (Boy et al. 2019,
90 Möller et al. 2019, Aðalgeirsdóttir et al. 2020, Gunnarsson et al. 2021, Meinander
91 et al. 2022). High precipitation rates across most of the southern Iceland (over
92 $5000 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$) (Crochet et al. 2007) also further increase the dynamism of its
93 glacial environment. Consequently, there are several different environmental
94 factors, including natural climate variability, geothermal activity, high dust
95 deposition rate and the complex topography of the glaciated terrain, that makes
96 Icelandic glacier dynamics especially complex to understand. Furthermore, that
97 complexity is potentially exacerbated with the formation and evolution of ice-
98 marginal lakes (Aðalgeirsdóttir et al. 2020). Ice-marginal lakes have formed across
99 Iceland in recent decades (Evans and Orton, 2015; Dell et al. 2019; Guðmundsson
100 et al. 2019; Baurley et al. 2020; Chandler et al. 2020), but little is known about

101 their short term evolution and intra-seasonal dynamics and the control of the lake
102 on glacier dynamics. The aim of this study is therefore to quantify the inter-annual
103 trends and intra-seasonal variation in glacier dynamics in the vicinity of an ice-
104 marginal lake.

105 **1.1. Study site**

106 Kvíárjökull is one of Iceland's most dynamic glaciers, with spatially-variable flow
107 rates and heterogeneous ice surfaces that are prone to degradation (Phillips et al.
108 2017). Kvíárjökull flows from the southeast of the Vatnajökull ice cap in southeast
109 Iceland (Figure 1a,b). The accumulation area (Figure 1c, A) is positioned at an
110 altitude of approximately 1800 to 1900 m a.s.l. and the glacier snout flows towards
111 the coastal plain (Figure 1c, Co), almost at the sea level. The Little Ice Age (LIA)
112 maximum extent of Kvíárjökull was in the mid-18th century, and there was little
113 change in its extent until the 1880s (Hannesdóttir et al., 2015). Using aerial
114 photography, Bennett et al. (2010) described the evolution of the glacier system
115 since the 1940s and identified periods of hiatus that punctuate an overall trend of
116 retreat. The lateral moraines are reported to be the biggest in Iceland
117 (Thórarinnsson 1956), and are most likely due to high rates of debris turnover
118 (Eyles 1979), with that debris sourced from steep volcanic rock walls positioned
119 alongside the glacier terminus. These lateral moraines are interpreted to have
120 originated during the Neoglacial, around 3200 yr BP (Spedding and Evans, 2002).
121 During that time the two major former meltwater outlets that cut through the
122 lateral moraines in both the northern (Figure 1c, On) and southern (Figure 1c, Os)
123 parts of the glacier were formed. The present position of these outlets is now
124 several tens of metres above the present day glacier surface. The current outlet
125 passes through the moraine and is located in the east (Figure 1c, Oe). The water
126 flowing out of the glacier is first stored in an ice-marginal lake and then drains
127 through the moraine towards the sea (approximately 2 km away).

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130 The present glacier foreland, bounded by its Neoglacial moraines, is predominantly
131 composed of glaciofluvial sediments that have aggraded sufficiently to partially
132 bury the downwasting glacier terminus. The ice is supplied from the accumulation
133 zone through a relatively narrow corridor (700-900 m wide, ca 2500 m long)
134 located along the central axis of the glacier, resulting in relatively high flow
135 velocities (Phillips et al. 2017). Unlike the central part, the margins are relatively
136 stable with low flow velocities, especially in its frontal zone. A number of
137 intermittent proglacial lakes were formed in the glacier foreland as a result of
138 downwasting of ice-cored moraines throughout the 20th century, although none
139 were reported to have formed on the foreland in 1998 (Bennett et al., 2010). Ice
140 mass loss has driven the formation of the present lake and the expansion of that
141 especially in the left lateral zone (Figure 1d,e) of the glacier since 2003 (Bennett
142 et al. 2010).

143 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

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146 A set of remote sensing data was used to describe glacier surface elevation
147 changes, ice flow velocity and areal fluctuation of the ice-marginal lake between
148 2011 and 2021. This was complemented by more detailed study of glacier intra-
149 seasonal dynamics in the summer 2021.

153 **2.1. Datasets**

154 **2.1.1. Satellite images**

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156 We used satellite-derived data to calculate interannual and interseasonal changes
157 in glacier velocity (see section 2.2), measure changes in glacier surface elevation
158 (section 2.3), and to delimit lake area (section 2.4). For the period 2011 to 2016,
159 we used 2m resolution ArcticDEM strips downloaded from the Polar Geospatial Data
160 Center at the University of Minnesota (Porter et al. 2018). From 2016 to 2021, we
161 used Sentinel-2 (MultiSpectral Instrument, MSI) images downloaded from
162 SentinelHub. To derive lake area between 2010 and 2015 we used Landsat-7
163 (Enhance Thematic Mapper plus, ETM+) and Landsat-8 (Optical Land Imager, OLI)
164 images, also from SentinelHub.

165 **2.1.2. UAV images**

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167 We conducted two UAV campaigns: **i)** 28 to 29 June 2021 and; **ii)** 2 September
168 2021 to understand intra-seasonal dynamics. Both UAV campaigns used a DJI
169 Mavic 2 Pro quadcopter equipped with a Hasselblad L1D-20c camera. The
170 physical focal length of the camera is 10.37 mm (focal length 28 mm in 35 mm
171 format equivalent). The camera has a 1" CMOS sensor, 20 million effective pixels,
172 and is mounted on a 3-axis gimbal. Although the UAV has a GNSS sensor, we
173 found it to be imprecise. Therefore, we used several ground control points (GCPs).
174 To ensure the GCPs were stable and not removed by strong wind, we used large
175 standalone rocks that we could easily identify from the image. This had the added
176 benefit that it prevented the pollution that lost artificial GCPs would cause. We
177 measured the position of each GCP before each measurement with a Trimble
178 GeoExplorer 6000 Series: Geo XH 3,5G. 120. We processed this data in the Trimble
179 GPS Pathfinder Office software and this showed us that the GCPs had not moved.

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181 Overall, we flew ten survey flights in each campaign that ensured the complete
182 coverage of the frontal part of the glacier and its direct surroundings. A single flight
183 lasted ~ 20 minutes and the flight parameters and automatic flight plan were
184 produced using the DJI GO 4 and Pix4Dcapture software. The camera and flight
185 parameters are summarised in Table 1. We captured 2,432 images during the June
186 campaign and 2,476 images during the September campaign.

187 **2.2. Glacier velocity**

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189 We used both manual and automatic approaches to calculate glacier ice velocity.
190 The manual method entailed us inspecting the change in position of 20 reference
191 points between pairs of images. We conducted this using ArcticDEM (2011 to 2016)
192 and Sentinel-2 (2016 to 2021) images. This was complemented by annual ice flow
193 velocity (automatic approach) derived from Sentinel-1 SAR data produced by
194 ENVEO (<https://cryoportal.enveo.at/project/CISIM/>). More detailed information on
195 the ice flow velocity product can be found in Wuite et al. (2022). We extracted the
196 average value for the whole glacier area as defined by Randolph Glacier Inventory
197 version 6 (RGI Consortium, 2017) for each of the years studied.

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199 Using the existing dataset provides us with more accurate picture of the spatial
200 variability of the ice flow velocities, whereas the manual approach enabled us to
201 prolonged the timeseries prior to the SAR Sentinel-1 images, i.e. prior to 2014.
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2.3. *Interannual surface elevation changes*

We defined two stable areas in the direct neighborhood of the glacier for comparison, we used individual pairs of DEMs to analyse surface elevation change. The overall size of the two selected stable areas was approximately 1 km². The maximum difference between these DEMs in Z-coordinate was 0.105 meters. We have summarised the stable area z-coordinate (elevations) differences between individual DEMs in Table 2.

Two ArcticDEM strips with the most complete coverage were used to evaluate longterm surface elevation changes. We used the data from 6 October 2012 and 19 March 2016.

2.4. *Changes in lake area*

We used the optical satellite images to manually delineate the areal changes of the Kvíárjökull ice-marginal lake. For the pre-Sentinel era (2010-2015), we used Landsat-7 and Landsat-8 images, with the higher resolution Sentinel-2 images used for the 2016-2021 period. The manual measurement of the lake area contains error related to the resolution of the original image. We assume that the Sentinel-2 (10 m resolution) manual delineation contains an error of +-5 m, similarly, the Landsat-7 and Landsat-8 (30 m resolution) contains an error of +-15 m. As a result, the total uncertainty of the lake area time series can be estimated by accounting for error propagation to be on average 0.024 km². This corresponds to approximately 4 % relative error when considering the lake area to fluctuate around 0.6 km² (see Results section). For all interannual comparisons and analyses, we used images taken in the end of August or beginning of September.

2.5. *Glacier and lake intraseasonal dynamics*

We processed the UAV images using the Structure from Motion (SfM) method in Agisoft Metashape to produce 2.5D and 3D models from our set of 2D images (Ozyesil, 2017). We conducted a quality control of all images in Agisoft before the analysis itself. Of the 4,908 images acquired, we found 109 to be of poor quality due to feeble blur. These were all from the June campaign. However, we still incorporated these images as they occurred in a single narrow strip and their removal would have resulted in a "no data" strip in the resulting model.

We then generated a sparse point cloud from the images, using the GNSS on board the UAV. We used key and tie points from across the dataset, and manually corrected the location of the GCPs, to ensure the images were well-aligned and accurate. We also improved the final accuracy of the model by incorporating the calibration properties of the camera. Finally, we created a dense point cloud and generated a texture to produce a DEM for each campaign. We then subtracted the DEM from the September campaign from the June campaign DEM to assess changes in glacier surface elevation during this period. The final parameters of the models are shown in Table 3.

We also visually inspected the UAV orthophotos to identify changes in the glacier-lake margin and changes in the adjacent proglacial areas.

2.6. Methodology and accuracy issues

Using a combination of different remote sensing products (ArcticDEM, Sentinel-2, UAV) has proved to be a useful approach for describing the dynamics of the frontal part of a glacier. Most of the previous studies detecting high spatial and temporal resolution glacier changes worldwide used a single data source (e.g. Barr et al. 2018 in Kamchatka; Malecki 2021 in Svalbard; Immerzeel et al. 2014 in Himalaya; Wang et al. 2021 in Tien Shan; or Ioli et al. 2021 in the Alps). However, these datasets are usually only available for a limited time; therefore, a combination of different data sources is usually used for long-term studies (e.g. Belart et al. 2019 in Iceland; Kavan et al. 2022 in Svalbard; Albedyll et al. 2018 in Greenland). Apart from airborne images, time-lapse photography has appeared as a powerful tool for analysing glacier-related processes in high temporal resolution (e.g. Mallalieu et al. 2017; How et al. 2019; Taylor et al. 2023). Oblique aerial or even terrestrial historic photographs might also be used for the reconstruction of early 20th-century glacier characteristics where more appropriate image material is lacking (Bjork et al. 2012; Girod et al. 2018; Holmlund and Holmlund, 2019; Kavan 2020). Here, we took advantage of multitemporal images and DEMs available within the last decade and combined them to obtain a complex view of the Kvíárjökull glacier front; including retreat rate, surface elevation changes, ice flow velocity, ice-marginal lake evolution and the development of different geomorphic features in the proglacial zone. A comparison of ArcticDEM individual strips was a simple and effective way to analyse surface elevation change and resulted in low errors (see Table 1). The GCPs used for UAV campaigns were not equally distributed because of the inaccessibility of the glacier surface. The GCPs were located in the glacier margins and proglacial zone. While this may result in high absolute elevation errors, especially in the central part of the glacier that was the most distant from the GCPs, the error is consistent between both UAV campaigns. Similar constraints with unequal distribution of GCPs when studying glacier surface changes are relatively frequent (e.g. Wang et al. 2021; Immerzeel et al. 2014; Fugazza et al. 2018). The accuracy of the DEM decreases with the distance to the closest GCP. Gindraux et al. (2017) found the rate of accuracy decrease typically of 0.09 m per 100-m distance over a glacier surface. This means in our case that the vertical error in the centre of the glacier (about 1000 m from the nearest GCP) could be about 1 m. We argue that the heterogeneous nature of the glacier surface with crevasses and other visible distinctive features (Figures 1, 6, 8) has been favourable in terms of precision of the point cloud generation. Despite that, it is necessary to be cautious when interpreting changes in the central part of the study area where the uncertainties are largest.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Lake surface area

Stable hydrological conditions were observed between 2010 and 2011, followed by a significant increase in areal extent between 2011 and 2012 (from 0.43 km² to 0.66 km² i.e. 35 % increase) following a 200 m retreat of the glacier terminus in the southern part of the glacier terminus (Figure 2b). Since 2012, the lake area has been mostly stable; fluctuating around 0.6 km². However, the ice-marginal length has been highly variable over the same period. This variability coincides with the retreat and advance of the glacier terminus and is particularly evident in

306 the southern part. The northern part of the lake shore is more stable, likely due to
307 thicker ice and consequently well-stabilised grounded glacier terminus. The lake
308 shoreline adjacent to the frontal moraine is relatively stable, which we interpret to
309 be due to the presence of vegetation, which has consolidated sediments. Some
310 other minor changes in shoreline position likely occurred due to local slope
311 deformation in steep parts of the shore.

312 **3.2. Surface elevation changes in 2012–2016**

313 A general thickening (Figure 3) occurred over much of the glacier. Thinning was
314 largely confined to the southeastern sector of the frontal zone ("SE" in Figure 3),
315 which is rather flat and subjected to frequent calving (as seen e.g. from Sentinel
316 images in Figure 4b). The northern part of the frontal sector („NE" in Figure 3) had
317 a very uneven surface in both years (2012 and 2016) and the resulting changes
318 were very spatially variable, with thickening in some places and thinning in others.
319 A similar spatial pattern was observed in the case of the moving esker (marked as
320 "esker" in Figure 3 and identified by Phillips et al. 2017). As a result, the shape of
321 the esker is very clearly identifiable on both DEMs and the final difference model.
322 This makes the esker a good marker for observing glacier movement, as the
323 changes in surface elevation highlight that the glacier has moved from its 2012
324 position, as highlighted by the loss of elevation in this region.
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328 **3.3. Glacier surface velocity**

329 Average glacier surface velocity at the glacier terminus was $104.3 \text{ m}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ in the
330 period 2012 – 2022. The velocity was, however, rather variable and was relatively
331 low in the early part of the observation period, followed by a large increase in
332 velocity in 2018 and 2019. We recorded the minimum surface velocity ($51 \text{ m}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$)
333 in 2015 and the maximum in 2018 ($199 \text{ m}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$) (Figure 2b). The average
334 velocity derived from Sentinel-1 SAR images (Wuite et al. 2022) is more
335 homogeneous but still within the values obtained by manual measurement (Figure
336 2b).
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339 We observed the maximum velocity in the upper reaches of the glacier, where the
340 ice surface gradient is greatest (15° in average) and the glacier is most constrained
341 through a narrow corridor (700 – 900 m). This terrain configuration likely enhances
342 the downward movement of the glacier. In the lower reaches, we observed a low
343 ice flow velocity (see Figure 5). A possible mechanism for this is that the mass of
344 the ice is less constrained close to the terminus, thus reducing the stress on the
345 ice and consequently reducing its velocity.
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348 The fact that ice flow velocities follow a transverse profile, i.e. the highest velocities
349 in the centreline compared to the lateral zones (Figure 5), suggests the importance
350 of internal deformation of the ice mass (Jennings and Hambrey 2021). The highest
351 flow velocities occur in the areas where there is sufficient mass/pressure from
352 upper parts of the glacier to cause deformation. We saw this expressed by
353 numerous crevasses in the central part of the narrow corridor (Figure 1f). The
354 frontal part of the glacier, where the ice flow velocity decreases, is relatively flat
355 and the surface is homogeneous without significant crevassing (compare with
356 Figure 6 a,b).
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3.4. 2021 ablation season dynamics

The relatively short period of observation from 28/29 June to 2 September 2021 was characterised by significant changes in the glacier terminus position i.e. glacier areal extent, surface elevation changes and changes in the adjacent proglacial geomorphology as a result of fluvial erosion.

3.4.1. Glacier areal extent changes

We identified the most pronounced changes in the southern part of the glacier terminus, close to the position of the calving front. A relatively large part of the glacier had disintegrated between the two UAV campaigns, which resulted in a retreat of more than 100 m in the most pronounced case (Figure 6c). The northern part of the frontal zone was stable and we only observed minor changes caused by lateral moraine slope failures following the thawing of ice-cored debris cover (Figure 6).

3.4.2. Surface elevation changes

We saw a large thinning of the frontal part of the glacier (Figure 7). Despite the above-zero air temperatures with average 9.6°C between the two UAV campaigns (see Supplementary data 1) suggesting that melting, and therefore surface lowering, would be widespread across the entire frontal part, we observed a minor increase in surface elevation in its northern margin. This is perhaps due to an inflow of ice from the higher portions of the glacier; an interpretation supported by our observation of slow down of glacier movement in this zone (Figure 5b). The contrasting behaviour of the northern and southern glacier margins can be explained by the variation in lake depth across the glacier margin. The northern part of the glacier terminus sits on the bedrock whereas the southern part is calving into the lake and is likely to be floating.

3.4.3. Proglacial landform evolution

Changes in the morphology of the highly dynamic lateral and frontal zones of the glacier were both widespread and profound. In regions where the foreland is in direct contact with the glacier body, degradation of ice-cored lateral moraines, development of several new kettle lakes and enlargement of already existing lakes was observed (Figure 8h,i). The northern section of the glacier terminus has a large quantity of supraglacial debris. Consequently, this section has become more stable and has begun to transition from debris-covered glacier into ice-cored moraine, with slope processes becoming more important than glacier dynamics to the evolution of its morphology (Figure 8b,c).

We also observed a spatial variability in the formation of lakes and the development of meltwater channels (Figure 8f,g). The variability in supraglacial debris is a possible mechanism that could explain this heterogeneity. On the eastern shore of the lake, adjacent to the Neoglacial frontal moraine, we did not observe evidence of glacial erosion. However, mass movement affects the relatively steep shore zone, as illustrated in Figure 8d,e.

4. DISCUSSION

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4.1. Glacier dynamics and lake interaction

Despite their importance on glacier movement, there is still some debate over the origin of the complex system of crevasses on Kvíárjökull. Phillips et al. (2017) presented a model of the active axial zone of the glacier surrounded by lateral and latero-terminal parts with slow movement. The active axial zone is not moving as a whole, but rather as individual sections with surge-like movements. These complicated shear stress processes inside the glacier led to the development of a strike-slip shear zone in the termino-glacial zone and the clockwise rotation of the ice-cored esker into its concertino shape deformation (as described by Knudsen 1995). However, Swift and Jones (2018) did not agree with this mechanism and suggested that the driving mechanism for glacier flow, surface crevassing and shape deformations reflect the complex subglacial topography.

We argue that another important driving factor on glacier dynamics is the ice-marginal lake itself, especially its southern basin. The lake shoreline evolution shows that the northern part of the glacier advanced to its northeastern forefield about 5–6 years after the abrupt extension of the lake (Figure 2b). It therefore appears that the lake expansion caused a speed up of glacier thinning and eventually complete disintegration of the southern latero-terminal glacier zone adjacent to the active axial zone, as defined by Phillips et al. (2017). The thermo-mechanical processes by which the lake promoted glacier thinning and ice margin collapse cannot be elucidated by our study and are complex and inter-linked (c.f. Carrivick et al., 2020). Propagation of lake water beneath and into the lowermost parts of the glacier is likely, for example, and would affect basal temperature, pressure and shear stress. What we can determine, is that degradation of the passive lateral zone of the glacier created space for the active axial zone, which was, until then, blocked. The axial zone of the glacier consequently sped up its movement and advanced rapidly. The 5–6 years of delay was necessary for the degradation of the passive latero-terminal zone.

However, Philipps et al. (2017) identified the main pulses of flow as towards the northeast. In 2018, the glacier advanced towards the northeast, which resulted in the narrowing of the central part of the connection between its southern and northern basins. This movement supports the existence and activity of the longitudinal shear zone between the axial and latero-terminal zone of the terminus (as described by Phillips et al. 2017). The shear zone directed the advance of the axial zone to the northeast. In the absence of the shear zone, the glacier would probably advance in the direction of the main flowline (as described by Swift and Jones, 2018) to the present lake, where it would cause the major thrusting described in the 1990s (Bennett et al. 2010). Dell et al. (2019) identified similar dynamic behaviour in Fjallsjökull (a neighbouring glacier sharing a common ice cap as an accumulation area) with the existence of localised flow 'corridors', which conveyed relatively faster flow towards the glacier's terminus. Spatially complex behaviour has also been attributed to site-specific factors, such as basal topography.

The stability of the shoreline adjacent to the Neoglacial frontal moraine contrasts with the variability of the shoreline adjacent to the glacier itself. We attribute many of the shoreline position changes adjacent to the glacier to the retreat and advance of the glacier (Figure 2). Such variable shoreline position has also been described

460 in other Icelandic glaciers, such as at the Jökulsárlón ice-marginal lake, about
461 15 km from Kvíárjökull, where Baurley et al. (2020) reported an increase in lake
462 areal extent of $\sim 20 \text{ km}^2$ since 1982 following a massive retreat of the glacier front
463 of up to 3.5 km. Similarly, an ice-marginal lake has also increased in size
464 significantly since a large re-advance in the 1990s after which the retreat exceeded
465 $35 \text{ m}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ (Chandler et al. 2020).

466
467 The ice-contact shoreline in the southern lake basin was uneven and jagged after
468 2012 because water inundated the complex system of cracks in the glacier front.
469 This unusual shoreline morphology has also been recorded in previous iterations
470 of the Kvíárjökull lake (1964, 1980, 2003, as described by Bennett et al. 2010)
471 and we interpret this to mark the transition of the lake from supraglacial towards
472 proglacial. This is contrasted by the northern lake, where the ice-contact shoreline
473 is more even and stable, likely because it is bound by an ice-cored push moraine,
474 which runs parallel to the lake shoreline (Phillips et al. 2017). These contrasting
475 shorelines have been characteristic of the lakes since at least 2003 (Bennett et al.
476 2010) and persisted until 2020. As described in Figure 2b, the shoreline
477 morphology changed following the calving of a large portion of ice in the southern
478 lake and this likely represents a shift in lake type, from supraglacial to ice-
479 marginal, and calving has begun to be the leading process of frontal ablation along
480 the whole southern ice-contact shoreline.

481
482 Kvíárjökull experienced several episodes of rapid advances between 1985 and
483 1990, followed by smaller advances between 1990 and 1998 (Phillips et al. 2017).
484 Phillips et al. (2017) also describe that at the same time, the ice-marginal lake
485 area fluctuated in front of the southern part of the glacier front. The lake has also
486 previously partly inundated the flat and thin regions of the glacier front (c.f. Figure
487 6d,e), potentially destabilising the glacier front. The presence of the lake in the
488 southern glacier forefield is facilitated by the existence of a bedrock overdeepening
489 (Magnússon et al. 2012). The abrupt increase of lake areal extent in 2012–2013
490 was caused by inundating of the fan-shaped system of radial and concentric
491 crevasses in the glacier marginal zone (south of the ice-cored esker). Lake
492 expansion coincided with a slowdown of the glacier flow velocity. The glacier
493 started to move towards the northeast in 2018 and this has resulted in the lake
494 separating into two distinct basins: a small northern basin and a large southern
495 basin (Fig 2b). A pulse of fast advance recorded in the period 2012–2013 (Phillips
496 et al. 2017) occurred shortly after an important and abrupt expansion of the
497 southern lake basin and the disintegration of the flat, thin marginal zone of the
498 glacier.

499
500 Glaciers terminating in lakes often recede more rapidly than their land-terminating
501 counterparts (e.g. Tsutaki et al. 2019) and lose mass by frontal ablation (Watson
502 et al. 2020, Sutherland et al. 2020). Even though Kvíárjökull glacier presents
503 similar characteristics to other lake-terminating glaciers, it does not follow this
504 general trend and we have found that its frontal position stays relatively stable as
505 well as the surface elevation. We attribute this to high ice flow velocity bringing
506 large ice masses towards its frontal margin. We observe the transfer of meltwater
507 from the lake to the glacier, as is shown on the orthophoto (Figure 6d,e), where
508 the intrusion of lake water into the crevassed glacier front is clear. The interaction
509 between the lake and the glacier can further enhance some of the processes that
510 are already in action. Baurley et al. (2020) emphasised that a calving front and
511 the presence of lake water can accelerate the flow velocity of glaciers. This

512 enhanced ice flow can be amplified by the presence of a deep reverse-sloping
513 subglacial trough. This could happen Kvíárjökull in the future because its subglacial
514 trough is relatively large and deep and further retreat of the glacier may lead to
515 the formation of a ca. 4 km² lake (Magnússon et al. 2012).

516

517 **4.2. Surface elevation change and mass balance**

518

519 Most of the glaciers in Iceland have lost mass over the last two decades
520 (Aðalgeirsdóttir et al. 2020). However, the frontal parts of Kvíárjökull do not
521 appear to have followed this same trend. While parts of the glacier terminus have
522 shown thinning between 2012 and 2016 (Figure 5), most of the area covered by
523 our analysis is relatively stable or is increasing in thickness. Nevertheless, it is
524 important to consider that the present-day surface morphology of the glacier is a
525 product of both surface lowering, as a product of melt, and ice mass thickening,
526 as a product of ice movement from the accumulation zone of the glacier.
527 Consequently, the ice mass lost during positive air temperature in the summer is
528 compensated for by an inflow of ice from the glacier's accumulation zone, thus
529 leading to a long-term quasi-equilibrium state of the glacier terminus.

530

531 Most of the changes were directly related to the flow of the glacier and
532 deformations of the ice mass (Phillips et al. 2017) due to the glacier overdeepening
533 as reported by Magnússon et al. (2012) and steep reverse slope in the terminus
534 zone (Phillips et al. 2017). It seems that the bedrock topography and continuous
535 inflow of the mass from the upper parts of the glacier are the controlling factors of
536 the surface elevation changes. The effect of climatic factors seems to be of second
537 order as no systematic thinning was observed despite the increasing air
538 temperatures (Fig 3). The accumulation-to-ablation ratio (AAR) of Kvíárjökull has
539 a value of 0.64 (Hannésdóttir et al., 2015), which is typical for Icelandic glaciers,
540 however, the high turnover rate (Bradwell et al. 2013) means the ice flow still
541 compensates for the high ablation (Eyles 1979). This is confirmed by only 0.27
542 m.year⁻¹ of average surface lowering reported between 2010-2019 compared to
543 0.42 m.year⁻¹ on the neighbouring Fjallsjökull, 0.49 m.year⁻¹ on Svinefellsjökull or
544 the Iceland average of 1.03 m.year⁻¹ (Hugonnet et al. 2021). The deformation of
545 ice mass driven by bedrock topography results in the complex spatial pattern of
546 surface elevation changes.

547

548 Calving is responsible for a substantial part of the overall mass loss of the glaciers
549 in contact with lakes (Benn et al. 2007). At Kvíárjökull, calving was responsible for
550 more than 100 m of glacier retreat during the 2021 summer season (Fig. 6c). The
551 interactions between the glacier and ice-marginal lake are quite complex and
552 include multiple feedbacks with high spatiotemporal variability. As a result, this
553 feedback may have led to enhanced melting of the frontal zone, especially through
554 meltwater exchange and lake water temperature effects (Carrivick et al. 2020).

555

556 Another factor controlling surface elevation changes is debris cover. This affects
557 the surface energy balance by providing the glacier surface with insulation when
558 the layer exceeds a certain thickness (Nicholson and Benn, 2013, Dragosic et al.
559 2016, Ben-Yehoshua et al. 2022, Meinander et al., 2022), which can reduce
560 surface melting. However, if debris cover is present in tandem with ice cliffs (Buri
561 et al. 2016) and supraglacial ponds (Miles et al. 2017), the opposite effect may
562 occur, with more pronounced melting as vertical surfaces are exposed. The
563 northern part of the glacier front is covered by debris (Figure 1). This debris cover

564 coincides with a thickening (Figure 7), similar to observations at Svínafellsjökull in
565 2021 (Ben-Yehoshua et al. 2022). It seems probable that the debris-covered part
566 of the glacier was protected from surface melting between the two UAV campaigns
567 in the summer of 2021, which resulted in the highly spatially variable glacier
568 surface elevation change (pronounced lowering in the southern part and stability
569 or even increase in the northern part). The substantial thinning in the southern
570 part during 2021 summer was likely caused by extremely high air temperatures
571 with the highest average summer air temperatures measured at several stations
572 around Vatnajökull (+3°C anomaly in July and August relative to 2011-2020, IMO,
573 2022).

574 **4.3. Proglacial zone terrain alterations**

575
576
577 The proglacial zone in direct contact with the glacier margin is often the most
578 active in terms of terrain alterations (Carrivick et al. 2022). The rate of change in
579 the ice-cored moraine is affected primarily by the angle of slopes and the presence
580 of meltwater streams (Ewertowski and Tomczyk 2015). These complex factors are
581 fully responsible for the development of the northern part of the glacier terminus.
582 The degradation of dead ice within the LIA frontal moraine, which formed between
583 130 and 140 years ago, is likely to have ceased. Consequently, this landscape is
584 beginning to stabilise and only minor slope processes can be detected in this
585 region. Conversely, the lateral ice-cored moraines are affected by intense marginal
586 meltwater and the stream often actively undercuts its slopes. The Neoglacial
587 frontal moraine is not affected by these streams because of the presence of the
588 proglacial lake, which redistributes the fluvial energy across the area of the lake
589 and tempers the rate of erosion, limiting it to only downwasting and backwasting
590 as a result of slow dead ice thawing (Kjær and Krüger 2001). It is likely that
591 without the lake the frontal moraine would undergo more intense fluvial erosion
592 with slope undercutting and probably lower the whole moraine ridge. We argue
593 that the protection of the Neoglacial frontal moraine by the existence of the ice-
594 marginal lake has helped to preserve the exceptionally large moraine ridge (e.g.
595 Thórarinnsson 1956). The only relatively active zone susceptible to erosion is the
596 lake shoreline itself, where wave action is responsible for the destabilisation of the
597 shore and has intensified slope movements. We identified erosion of the lake
598 shoreline adjacent to the glacier during a single summer melt season, which others
599 have also identified at glaciers in different parts of the world (e.g. Fu et al. 2022;
600 Zhong et al. 2022). Here, the changes in the marginal zone are expressed in the
601 formation of kettle lakes, or the widening of existing ones, as well as the activation
602 of slope processes.

603
604

5. CONCLUSIONS

606 Kvíárjökull is a glacier that has a complex topography, comprising a steep and
607 narrow corridor connecting the accumulation area to the terminus, and is situated
608 in a temperate region with high precipitation rates and high summer air
609 temperatures. Consequently, this glacier system is highly dynamic and
610 characterised by high ice flow velocity. This highly dynamic system has undergone
611 varied rates of terminus retreat and glacier thinning, and these changes, along
612 with ice flow velocities, coincide with the extent of its proglacial lake. Specifically,
613 increased lake extent coincides with decreased glacier velocity. The disintegration
614 of a large portion of ice in the southern lake in 2020 likely represents a shift in
615 lake functioning. Calving has begun to be the leading process of frontal ablation
616 along the whole southern ice-marginal lake shoreline.

617 The northern part of the glacier terminates on land and has a substantial debris-
618 cover. This part was stable without any significant surface thinning, even
619 experiencing slight elevation increase (up to 5 m). The insulation effect of the
620 debris-cover and high input of ice mass from the accumulation zone probably
621 compensates for the mass loss caused by high summer air temperatures.
622 Conversely, the southern part of the glacier terminus lost up to 20 m from its
623 surface elevation during the summer of 2021. The ice-marginal lake in the
624 southern part introduced another mass loss process: calving, which we suggest
625 explains the enhanced ice mass loss and ice velocities at the southern margin of
626 the terminus. We also detected changes in the deglaciating foreland, where the
627 formation and widening of kettle lakes and minor landslides were detected during
628 the summer melt season of 2021.

629 In the future, the high ice flow velocities of (up to 200 m·year⁻¹), combined with
630 over deepening in the bedrock topography that make lake expansion possible,
631 may combine to accelerate glacier mass loss and retreat.

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1045 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

1046 *Conceptualization: JK, DN; Fieldwork: JK, RS, MR, JH, DN; Data*
1047 *processing: JK, RS; writing – initial draft: JK, RS, MH, CDS; writing –*
1048 *reviewing and editing: JLC, MR, JH, PDW, KL, DN; funding acquisition: JK,*
1049 *KL*

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1051 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

1052 *Satellite data used in the study are publicly available from Sentinel Hub*
1053 *(<https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>) and Polar Geospatial Center*
1054 *(<https://www.pgc.umn.edu/data/arcticdem/>). Ice flow velocity data are*
1055 *available from ENVEO (<https://cryoportal.enveo.at/project/CISIM/>), UAV*
1056 *based data are available on request.*

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Figure 1 – (a) Kviárjökull location within Iceland; (b) close up view of the Kviárjökull area as seen on a Sentinel-2 false colour image (10 September 2021); (c) the DEM of the glacier and its immediate surrounding based on an ArcticDEM strip from 22.09.2011 (gaps filled by data from 06.10.2012); A= accumulation zone; K= Kviárjökull terminus; Co= coastal plain; On= glacier meltwater outlet north; Oe= glacier meltwater outlet east; Os= glacier meltwater outlet south; (d) UAV view on the northern part of the lake with the debris covered lateral part of the glacier from the stabilised Neoglacial lateral moraine; (e) the debris covered glacier surface with large supraglacial lakes - northern part; (f) massive crevasses in the narrow corridor connecting the ice cap on top of the image; (g) with the frontal part glacier and the lake

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Figure 2 – glacier terminus retreat/advance resulted in changes of lake outline and also areal extent; (a) the situation of the lake as seen from Sentinel-2 image (10 September 2021) with the lake extent highlighted in green; (b) average ice flow velocity (both manually estimated and SAR derived), lake areal extent and ice-contact length evolution from 2010–2021

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Figure 3 – Comparison of the 2012 and 2016 ArcticDEM strips with the resulting difference model; the coloured scale expresses the elevation change in metres between 2012 and 2016 DEMs; the difference model is masked to the glacier extent, with the Sentinel-2 image (31/08/2021) used as a background.

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Figure 4 – Movement of the ice-cored esker in the central part of the glacier front as seen from ArcticDEMs (a) and Sentinel-2 images (b) (2011–2019); (c) interannual evolution of the esker shape and position.

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Figure 5 – (a) spatial pattern of ice flow velocity for Kvíárjökull and neighbouring glaciers (based on 2014-2021 Sentinel-1 SAR data produced by ENVEO – see chapter 2.2.), glacier outlines taken from RGI 6.0, Kvíárjökull highlighted in thick line; shaded relief derived from ArcticDEM used as background; (b) glacier movement between the two UAV campaigns in summer 2021 illustrated by the vectors of reference points displacement (in yellow)

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Figure 6 – (a) Orthophoto map of the frontal glacier zone from 28/29 June 2021; (b) 2 September 2021; (c) outline of the glacier front overlapped to a single image; (d,e) detail view of the southern frontal zone to illustrate the lake water intrusion into the crevassed ice field

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Figure 7 – Surface elevation change between June and September 2021 based on the DEMs derived from UAV mapping campaigns; the background image is the orthophoto map from September 2021.

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Figure 8 – (a) examples of the development of the proglacial zone during the 2021 ablation season. (b,c) the debris-covered northern part of the glacier terminus ; (d,e) landslide activation on the steep (up to 20°) shoreline adjacent to the Neoglacial frontal moraine; (f,g) development of lakes on the surface of the debris-covered glacier front accompanied by the disintegration of the shoreline; (h,i) development of kettle lakes at the southern glacier margin

1116 **Tables**

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1118 *Table 1 Camera and flight parameters (UAV campaigns).*

Camera parameters:	Flight parameters:
Camera maker: Hasselblad	Flight height: approx. 120 meters
Camera model: L1D-20c	Size of area: approx. 1600 x 1300 meters
Camera angle: 90°	Forward/side overlap: 80%/72%
Still Image size: 5472×3648 pix.	Type of scan: Single grid
Resolution: 72 dpi	GSD: approx. 0.028 meter
F-stop: f/4.0 – f/2,8	Speed: approx. 3 ms ⁻¹
Exposure time: 1/200 sec.	Time (only sensing): approx. 20 minutes
ISO: 100	Flight mode: automatic

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1123 *Table 2 Differences in Z-coordinates (elevations) within stable areas.*

YEAR	DIFFERENCE [METER]
2017 – 2016	-0.092
2016 – 2015	0.105
2015 – 2013	-0.021
2013 – 2012	0.017
2012 – 2011	0.057

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1126 *Table 3 Final parameters of computed models. Processing machine parameters:*

1127 *CPU - Intel Core i7-8750H, 2.20GHz, 6 Cores, 12 Logical Processors; RAM –*

1128 *16 GB; GPU – nVidia GeForce GTX 1060 with Max-Q Design, 6 GB.*

	<i>June campaign</i>	<i>September campaign</i>
<i>Involved images</i>	2336	2426
<i>Involved GCPs</i>	14	14
<i>Sparse point cloud</i>	4,770,503	7,692,576
<i>Dense point cloud</i>	182,043,255	230,479,851
<i>Number of faces</i>	35,219,766	45,579,980
<i>Orthophoto resolution</i>	0.05	0.05
<i>[meter]</i>		
<i>DEM resolution [meter]</i>	0.05	0.05
<i>RMSE [meter]</i>	0.113	0.345
<i>Computing time [hours]</i>	Approx. 23	Approx. 17

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